

A Study on Commerce Student’s Perspective towards E-learning with Reference to Bangalore South

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Abstract

In our daily life, we tend to learn from each and every experience even from the minute instances which is a never ending process. The new innovation and ideas in the field of technology has paved a way to the new world of learning things interestingly which is our E-learning. It is a need for the hour which is of great importance in order to gain world level knowledge which is playing an influential role. E-learning has enabled students to gain knowledge enthusiastically when compared to traditional classroom teaching. Through this paper we present our study on the concept on influence of E-learning on the education of under graduate students specifically in the commerce field at Bangalore South institutions which elaborates on the repercussions of technology which has helped the students to increase their knowledge. Though traditional classroom teaching is a must factor, E-Learning has become its important tool.

Keywords: E-Learning, Traditional Classroom Teaching, Commerce Students, Influence on Education, Enhancing Knowledge.

Introduction

Learning through the mode of electronic way is referred as E-learning which has become a need of the hour for the purpose of creative learning. It has a major role for the purpose of learning in every one’s life. It has paved a new way of learning. It is being used as a tool of knowledge wherein anyone can gain knowledge on a click of a button. E-learning is also known as the course, content or program delivered completely online which can also be referred as computerized learning, Distance education, online learning, internet learning and in many ways. It is mainly delivered through the creation of content, website (FedEx, MOOC, etc) and a proper channel of delivery. Each and every need of information can be availed through E-learning provided if is properly structured and explained. This mode of learning provides a platform for students to be independent in their learning process wherein they can have the access to the information at any time without any barriers. Nowadays the scope of e-learning has reached to a wider extent wherein all the ages of people are using this mode of learning to learn things.

Literature Review

Kiran Lata Dangwal (2018) enumerates that e-learning has greater flexibility with the implementation of Information and communication technology (ICT) where it can obtain education anywhere, anytime through the online system. ICT breaks all the barriers of traditional classroom teaching and learning process where all the new e-learning technologies empower all the learners irrespective of their diversities.

Zuleika Firdosh Homavazir (2015) found out that e-learning helps to create, deliver, and manage the activities of education and training. Online learning, Computer based learning, etc deliver the content of education via Internet. Intranet/extranet (LAN/WAN), audio and videotape, satellite broadcast, interactive TV.

Azimi, Hamid Mohamad (2014) studies the needs of faculty members and students of colleges for education in e-learning system, to evaluate their current knowledge of e-skills and show how colleges' readiness to use for implementation of e-learning into their teaching-learning process with the help of ICT infrastructure, human resources, finance and with the needs of new-line-learning components, e-skills.

Purpose of Research

The main reason behind this study is to explore how students are utilizing the technology for their learning purpose and its impact.

The Objective of the Study

1. To study the benefits of E-Learning.
2. To study the impact of E-Learning on Commerce students for enhancing their knowledge to face the competitive world.
3. To study the student's opinions on E-Learning.

Research Methodology

Type of research – This study is based on Descriptive method.

Sampling

1. Sample size - Sample size of 200 students have been taken for the study.
2. Sample unit – Individual students were studying Bachelor of Commerce stream.
3. Sample description – 20 students from 12 different colleges in Bangalore South are considered.
4. Sampling technique – For conducting the study, convenient and stratified random sampling is adopted.

Source of Data

This research is carried on through the primary source where data is gathered from B.com students from various institutions using Questionnaires.

Secondary data was collected from articles, publications, journals, and books from different websites on search engines available.

Data analysis and interpretation - Data was analyzed and interpreted with the help of charts and hypothesis applications.

Concept of E-learning

E-learning is the process of learning through utilizing electronic technology to access the educational curriculum apart from the traditional classroom learning. Most of the times it is

delivered live, wherein students can raise questions and solve their doubts then and there. Even in the mode of E-learning, there will be a teacher interacting with the students in order to assist them in their process of learning.

E-learning is a learning system which is based on formalized teaching with the help of electronic resources. It can also be referred as the network based transfer of skills and knowledge to the student who requires it without the restriction of time, geographical boundary, etc.

Research Hypothesis

In this study, four research hypotheses were examined to determine which should be accepted and which must be ignored.

H1: E-Learning is helping students to gain knowledge to meet the challenges on the global front through e-learning.

H2: Audio content is helpful for learning concepts in E-Learning

H3: Video content is the advantage for learning concepts in E-Learning.

H4: E-Learning is helping students to get certified for professional courses.

Benefits of E-learning

Due to the inbuilt benefits and technical ease, E-Learning has evolved to be the effective source of information and knowledge acquiring process. Hence some of its benefits can be as follows:

1. **Accessibility:** E-Learning is accessible 24/7 without any time constraint, which is boon to the learning process, which enables students to learn at any time when required.
2. **Best suited for everyone:** E-Learning is best suited to every one where anyone can access the content from a small child to elders.
3. **It can be repeated:** Unlike classroom teaching, in E-Learning, the content or the teaching video can be repeated several times until the learner understands the complete concepts.
4. **Updated content:** This is one of the benefits for these days learning in which we can access the updated information from any part of the world. Ex: in a subject like Income Tax, tax rates for every person keeps on changing from year to year according to the requirement of the content. Hence students can be updated by accessing the information through online websites, which will help them to be updated.
5. **Faster delivery of content:** Through the mode of E-learning, the content can be delivered quickly to the learners when it is compared to traditional method. Thereby the time taken to learn can be reduced to 25-60% than the regular classroom teaching.
6. **Cost can be reduced:** Learning through the mode of technology is cost effective when it is compared to the traditional forms of learning. Ex: The training time of the trainers can be reduced, the cost of course material, etc.
7. **Environmental friendly:** Learning through the internet is a paperless way and thereby it protects the environment a lot. A study reveals that the distance education has consumed around 90% less power and has generated 85% less amount of carbon dioxide emissions when compared to traditional teaching. Thus E-learning is highly eco-friendly way of learning.

Limitations of E-learning

1. No self-discipline

Respondents claim that the main advantage in E-learning is that it is self-paced. If you need a break during the session, you can pause the video and continue whenever you are interested. However, because of this freedom, it often translates into no learning, wherein the self-assessment questions, at the end of the session, can be skipped, or it can be taken lightly than when compared to the traditional learning mechanism.

2. Lack of Flexibility

E-learning can be a good opportunity for learning specific skills, but it is incredibly difficult to learn complex skills and competencies effectively.

3. Lack of Input from Trainers

E-learning is structured where a program is developed based on the developer ideology. When compared to the traditional learning system, teaching from trainers through the electronic mode is less efficient, wherein they can clarify the doubts which a student has but cannot understand the student completely.

4. Good E-Learning Requires Knowledge and Skills

Developing a proper and effective E-learning course consumes considerable time, money and, a good amount of experience as it requires multimedia, custom web development, technical support with technical user integration design.

5. No Peripheral Benefits

When there is a team of experts, we can get an opportunity for more than just learning; thereby, we will get more than the subject knowledge. In virtual learning, when it is structured, there is no such opportunity of getting peripheral benefit.

Findings

Impact of E-Learning on B. Com Students

This study is mainly intended to aim at the influence of E-Learning on the education of B. Com students.

148 respondents out of 200 samples collected are using E-Learning effectively for their learning purpose.

Students feel that they are getting exposure for them to learn things more effectively and enthusiastically.

Students are getting a varied field of knowledge where they can study without any time constraints.

Students are enhancing their skills by getting exposed to a different field of study.

Students can gain knowledge irrespective of their stream that is commerce students can learn computer science or photography, etc.

Analysis

In the above chart, student’s opinions on how E-learning is making them get prepared to meet the global challenges are drafted. Upon 200 students, a majority of 60 students believe that in rare cases, E-learning is effective.

Analysis

In the above chart, the majority of students are in the opinion that the audio content of E-learning is effective which, is making them listen and learn things effectively.

Analysis

The above chart depicts the view of students towards the video content of E-learning wherein the majority of the samples collected agree that the video content is also helpful for learning.

Analysis

The above chart represents that the students agree that through the mode of E-learning, they can pursue professional without any geographical barriers.

Overall Opinion

1. Out of 200 responses, 34 are enthusiastically interested in E-Learning to learn concepts other than syllabus specified, 64 are using E-Learning with some interest, and 52 are only to some extent. The rest of the respondents are using very rarely.
2. Forty seven respondents are motivated through the process to learn more, 52 are using with some interest, and 59 respondents are utilising to some extent.
3. Forty nine respondents felt that E-Learning helps them to gain knowledge other than classroom teaching, 51 respondents are making use of technology with some interest.
4. Thrity four responded that they can get information from joining various institutions enthusiastically for their further studies, 66 with some interest, 43 felt only to some extent.
5. The other respondents were not inclined towards learning through technology.

Study and Evaluation

In this study, the p-value has been used to test the above hypotheses. P-value is a probability statement which answers the question: If the Null Hypothesis is accepted, then what is the probability of becoming aware of the test statistics at least as extreme as the one observed.

A p-value of 0.05 or less rejects the null hypothesis ‘at the 5% level’ which means it suggests that only 5% of the time would the supposed this process to come to a finding to the utmost if the null hypothesis were accepted. 5% and 10% are significance levels to which p-values were compared.

While testing the 1st hypothesis, global challenges were kept in mind and where the result was statistically significant ($p\text{-value } 0.24 < 0.5$). Therefore it can be inferred that there is a relationship between E-Learning and the opportunity to face challenges on a global front. Through this analysis, it can be known that students enthusiastically feel that E-Learning is helping them to gain knowledge which assists them to meet global challenges.

2nd hypothesis is that the audio content of E-Learning is helpful where the data has revealed that p-value is less than 0.5 which, expresses the statistical significance ($H_3: p\text{value}=0.095008 < 0.5$) – this is accepted.

The 3rd hypothesis is also agreeing that the video content of E-Learning also enhances the effectiveness of their learning where the p-value is less than 0.5 ($H_4: p=0.127941 < 0.5$) which, is accepted.

The 4th hypothesis has also produced an accepted result where the p-value is less than 0.5 ($H_5: 0.104311 < 0.5$), which reveals that E-Learning is assisting the student to in getting them certified for professional courses.

Limitations of Study

1. The number of students selected for sampling is less when it is compared to the total strength of commerce students in South Bangalore.
2. The selected studnet’s opinion may not be the same with the rest of the students.
3. Because of Simple random sampling, studious students might be missed when collecting data

Suggestions

1. It is advised to the students to take up online courses through the mode of E-learning to enhance their knowlegde and qualification.
2. Developers of e-learning material should update themselves regularly so that the students can get theupdated information.
3. Trainers should handle the quality of audio and video content carefully.

4. Teachers, along with the classroom teaching, should encourage students to make use of E-learning to enhance their level of knowledge.

Conclusion

E-learning has been accepted to be a successful method of training and education along with our traditional teaching. The institutions which use E-learning are a way ahead of those who have not yet adopted the technique of E-learning. There is no doubt that it is equally important to consider the non-electronic teaching with the assistance of books and projects, but the effectiveness and efficiency of technology based learning cannot be ignored completely. The one thing that is observed in this study is that those students who are using E-learning are quite confident enough in their level of knowledge and the information about the current affairs along with their curriculum. Therefore E-learning should be adopted by each and every student in order to enhance their level of educational qualification, skills and knowledge.

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